

Disentangling international research collaboration in the Spanish academic context: Is there a desirable researcher human capital profile?

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ABSTRACT

A number of studies has focused on examining those academic researchers attributes-demographics or not- that condition international research collaboration (IRC) and its results. However, it is not possible to speak about an 'ideal' type of researcher so far. Should we assume that just only those 'star researchers' collaborate internationally?. The literature is not clear enough on this topic, offering interesting but insufficient support to know the set of individual characteristics that ensures fruitful IRC. To deepen the analysis of academic researchers attributes, in particular, the human capital characteristics, this study proposes in-depth research on exploring different combinations on human capital dimensions and testing potential differences in IRC levels. To do so, from an exploratory perspective, a cluster analysis was conducted in a sample of 937 Spanish academics, obtaining three researcher profiles: (1) consolidated international research collaborators, (2) effective international research collaborators, and (3) skilled international research collaborators. Far from the recurrent analysis of single or disconnected researchers' attributes, this paper contributes to the extant literature with a new typology based on the variables of academic human capital, providing an useful starting point to better understand who really can develop international networks to collaborate and, therefore, how to foster IRC in Universities.

1. Introduction

International research collaboration (IRC) is a strategic priority for the European Union (European Commission and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). Its incalculable value and potential to contribute to science excellence is understood as the basis on which most important European funding programs are built. Horizon Europe, with a budget of €95.5 billion, rests on a "Team Europe" approach that promotes a common understanding of research and innovation with the aim to foster research networks. In particular, Pillar I (Excellence Science) of Horizon Europe will be developed—among other initiatives—through Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions with €6.6 billion supporting IRC by funding researchers' mobility and training.

Although one may expect that IRC always leads to positive results as more citations or impact (Langfeldt et al., 2015), some studies still show that this not always happens (Hayati and Didegah, 2010 cited in Chen et al., 2019). The complexity of the topic, due to the existence of a number of factors affecting IRC—political, economic, cognitive, spatial

and social—(Chen et al., 2019, p. 160), implies competing and even inconclusive results derived from the variety of perspectives and methodologies applied. So, in that context, do we really know how IRC works? What are the key determinants of international collaborations in reality? Why, in some cases, do top researchers not collaborate internationally? Although IRC has been studied for decades, a number of issues remain unclear in regard to how it works (Kwiek, 2020).

Aiming to shed more light on IRC functioning, this paper starts from the assumption that any advancement in knowledge and research "demands that the researcher be equipped with the appropriate competencies, beginning from knowledge about the problem under analysis [...]" (Abramo et al., 2017, p. 1017). This focus on the individual researcher in the IRC context leads us to propose a micro-level analysis of human capital to explore the different profiles of researcher attributes in international collaborations, affecting the creation of new knowledge and scientific publications. Although diverse investigations have studied individual predictors of IRC, such as age or gender (Kwiek, 2020), the literature analyzing researchers' attributes have not paid particular attention to

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how the combination of different human capital attributes may affect IRC levels and behaviors.

In doing so, we take arguments from the human capital literature but from a critical perspective. In fact, we question the traditional “more is better” approach, which assumes higher levels of human capital are always better and needed to show relevant IRC (Ployhart et al., 2014). In IRC dynamics, more than having high levels of human capital, a balanced combination of attributes would be more useful in developing international interactions and networks (Wright and McMahan, 2011; Crocker and Eckardt, 2014). This would be the “human capital profile” approach that presents a more realistic view of IRC, in which not only top researchers would develop IRC but also other skilled researchers with a balanced profile of human capital. This alternative approach is built on the traditional knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSA) framework (Becker, 1962) as an integrative perspective to examine human capital in the IRC context.

Therefore, this study contributes to the extant literature in the following two ways: (1) by providing a preliminary classification for international research collaborators based on researchers’ human capital, and (2) by suggesting an alternative perspective—a human capital profile approach—to study, in a more systematic way, individual researchers’ attributes in the IRC context.

In order to achieve these objectives, the paper develops an empirical analysis divided into three clear stages. First, to identify the individual attributes that make up research human capital, the design of the questionnaire began with a Delphi analysis, building a measurement scale about scientific human capital from an expert’s perspective of a panel of leading scholars. After obtaining an expert consensus on the relevant items that needed to be introduced in the measurement scale, in a second stage, we empirically validated the measurement tool extracted from the Delphi technique. Finally, in the third stage, we developed a k-means cluster analysis that was conducted to identify and describe the groups of academics in the sample. To analyze the relationship between these identified profiles and their IRC levels, ANOVA tests were also conducted.

The paper is structured as follows: (1) We review the existing literature on human capital in the IRC context and how it influences scientific productivity, (2) we conduct an exploratory k-means cluster analysis to describe researchers’ human capital configurations in a sample of 937 Spanish academics, and (3) we discuss the findings and implications of the study and propose future lines of research.

2. Theoretical development

2.1. IRC and scientific productivity

IRC, as a crucial phenomenon describing actual research advances, has received special attention in recent years (Chen et al., 2019; Kwiek, 2020). Scientific collaboration is a matter of social convention among researchers that is extremely complex in its definition since it varies over time and varies in its manifestations (Katz and Martin, 1997; Kwiek, 2020).

According to Kwiek (2020: 59), IRC can be defined as “an emergent, self-organizing, networked system, in which the selection of partners and research settings often relies on the researchers themselves.” Similarly, Jeong et al. (2011) point out that it is necessary to differentiate internal collaboration (within the same research team or university) from local or “domestic” collaboration (with colleagues from the same country) and international collaboration (with colleagues from other countries). Considering the implications of these types of collaboration, IRC is the most-used type of collaboration for a scientist since “it presupposes attractiveness, international visibility and, often, it implies a significant commitment on the part of the researcher” (Smeby and Gornitzka, 2008: 48).

The literature has shown that IRC is typically a critical predictor of high scientific productivity, while other “local” collaborations do not

always show a significant causal relationship (Kwiek, 2015). In this sense, in a study on highly productive academics in Europe, Kwiek (2016) concluded that “internationalization and collaboration” emerges as the most important determinant of research productivity.

Likewise, Abramo et al. (2011), drawing on data obtained from Italian scientists, showed that there is a positive relationship between the degree of IRC among academics and their individual scientific productivity, which in turn affects the intensity of international collaborations and the subsequent average quality of their publications.

Therefore, although there may not always be a causal relationship with scientific productivity, it seems clear that highly productive scientists tend to collaborate to a greater extent with international colleagues (Kwiek, 2019). This, to some extent, is explained because IRC is considered a relevant driver in the development of research. It facilitates access to unique human capital in different countries and serves as a means to find complementary capacities among researchers (Chen et al., 2019). The most international scientific teams enjoy greater experience and a wider variety of knowledge, which benefits the processes of generating scientific knowledge (Bercovitz and Feldman, 2011). An internationalized team expands cognitive frontiers and has access to a larger “search space” for knowledge, allowing greater access to more innovative ideas.

In this sense, the literature has also demonstrated that publications with international authors tend to have a greater impact, measured in higher citation rates (He, 2009; Adams, 2013; Wagner et al., 2017; Dusdal and Powell, 2021), what implies certain “bonus” based on the internationalization of the research itself, beyond the benefits of any scientific collaboration that extends the cognitive frontiers of a researcher (Kato and Ando, 2013). This may be because publishing with other international colleagues confers greater visibility to the published research, leading to a greater number of subsequent citations, which affects the impact of the research.

In addition, international collaborations, on many occasions, are developed with experts in a specific subject area who have important relevance in the field of knowledge in which they are considered scientific eminences. This leads to co-authors benefiting from the well-known “Matthew effect.” According to this effect, highly cited and visible researchers in a scientific field would also benefit, in turn, from the greater visibility and impact of their research feeding back to them (Langfeldt et al., 2015). Hence, IRC would offer the opportunity to increase the prestige and impact of research results published with international colleagues.

As observed, IRC’s potential to contribute to science and to improve researchers’ productivity is clear, therefore, a set of studies has gone a step further, identifying the factors that affect IRC (Pohl, 2020; Morley and Heraty, 2019; Fox et al., 2017). These factors usually include the academic discipline (Finkelstein and Sethi, 2014; Kyvik and Aksnes, 2015; Kwiek, 2018); the institutional type (Cummings and Finkelstein, 2012); the national reward structure (Dobbins and Kwiek, 2017); the type of university of affiliation (Cummings and Finkelstein, 2012); the academic cohort (or career stage) to which the collaboration belongs (Jung et al., 2014; Kwiek, 2020); the international research orientation, structures, and dynamics (Kwiek, 2018); researcher gender (Abramo et al., 2013); and other researcher attributes, such as human capital, motivations, and expertise.

Due to the enormous number of different factors conditioning IRC, the literature is, to a greater extent, dispersed. In fact, as Kwiek (2020) has identified, more specialized IRC literature can be structured into three main topics: 1) Institutional and contextual predictors of IRC (reward structures, academic fields, and working time); 2) Individual predictors of IRC (age, gender, rank, academic generation, and academic role orientation); and 3) Methodological issues (most IRC studies based on surveys and bibliometric research).

In this study, we mainly focus on the individual human capital attributes that are also present in IRC and that are considered the basis on which international collaboration is built (Abramo et al., 2017).

2.2. Human capital and IRC: a particular focus on the Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSA) framework

As mentioned, our initial assumption is that researchers' individual attributes—human capital, in particular—work as the origin of research collaborations (Abramo et al., 2017). In this vein, we question whether the 'ideal' combination of human capital attributes to foster IRC exists.

Along this line, as Kwiek (2020) recently posited, IRC highly depends on "the power of individual scientists." However, despite its recognized importance, there is also a clear dispersion in the extant literature regarding attributes of researchers that truly affect the generation of international research networks.

Bozeman and colleagues, among others, have offered tentative models in which scientific and technical human capital is explicitly considered as a determinant of research collaboration effectiveness (Bozeman et al., 2013; Bozeman et al., 2015). Nevertheless, due to the broad focus of these models, they do not offer a deep analysis about the particular researcher human capital attributes fostering IRC (Abramo et al., 2017).

Hence, following the aforementioned "human capital profile" approach and the application of the KSAs framework (Becker, 1962), a researcher classification will be provided to explore whether there is a certain combination of attributes that supports IRC better than others.

Despite human capital has been defined from a number of perspectives, the KSA framework is the most used manner of conceptualizing human capital at the individual level (Nyberg et al., 2014) (Please, see Appendix B for a summary of most relevant works per human capital dimension). The logic behind the KSAs approach is that not only researchers with high levels of human capital in all dimensions are able to deploy IRC but also researchers who show certain and balanced human capital attributes can implement IRC in searching for particular partners. Therefore, it can be said that IRC would lead researchers to seek out complementarity and efficient partners with whom to do research (Wagner, 2005; Kwiek, 2018), even between different disciplines (Rigby and Edler, 2005).

Applying the KSAs framework to the IRC context, collaborating internationally may help by complementing and integrating different types of *academic knowledge* (K) to generate new ideas and develop novel insights. In the academic context, knowledge is understood not only as "a certain justified belief" (Nonaka et al., 2000: 7) but also meaningful information (Nonaka et al., 2000); experience, context, reflection, and interpretation (Davenport and Prusak, 1998); and the analysis and reading of specific theories and explications and empirical results (Bozeman et al., 2001), as García-Carbonell et al. (in press) point out.

Accordingly, we introduce the notion of knowledge following the traditional distinction between *tacit knowledge*—also known as scientific knowledge—which includes in our context the theories and foundations of academic disciplines, and *explicit knowledge*, which is considered the knowledge related to methodology and research techniques (Bozeman et al., 2001).

It is widely recognized in the literature that having academic knowledge, of any type, leads to better research results (De Frutos-Belizón et al., 2019), such as by providing a higher number of publications or citations for a researcher (Jacob and Lefgren, 2011). In fact, research supported on weak knowledge of the topic and methodological and statistical processes tends to provide trivial contributions and is susceptible to major and deeper criticism (Mooken and Sugden, 2014).

Abramo et al. (2017) recognized that the basis on which research collaboration is built is composed of the individual knowledge about the problem under analysis and the knowledge to conduct rigorous analysis, using appropriate methodologies and reporting findings properly. Hence, collaborating generates synergies from complementary backgrounds and knowledge to create or select new ideas (Abramo et al., 2017: 1017).

The second dimension of human capital that can contribute to improved IRC entails *researchers' skills* (S). As Dusdal and Powell (2021)

hold, it is important to incorporate into one's work other researchers with new ideas and relevant skills in IRC. In contrast to research abilities, skills have a more generic nature, not explicitly related to research activities but particularly useful to be more productive in conducting research (De Frutos-Belizón et al., 2019). For instance, the literature considers communicative and idiomatic skills, leadership (McNie et al., 2016), coordination skills (Kyvik, 2013), and a researcher's ability to create networks to collaborate (Azoulay et al., 2017) as crucial attributes that support IRC to improve research results (Beaver, 2001).

Finally, the last antecedent of IRC may also arise from *researchers' abilities* (A). These attributes refer to the individual capacity to perform properly in a concrete job or profession—in the present case, doing research (Lindberg and Rantatalo, 2015). This dimension of human capital comprises hard academic skills that have to be acquired during the specific doctoral training. For instance, reaching scientific rigor and the ability to formulate hypotheses and communicate research results (McNie et al., 2016) are considered relevant attributes that affect research productivity. Moreover, other cognitive abilities are related to the capacity to analyze data to address research questions (Drummond and Fischhoff, 2017) and to teamwork and scientific collaboration processes (Bozeman et al., 2013).

3. Methodology

Although IRC has been widely studied, the description of the human capital of researchers who collaborate internationally remains unclear. Therefore, the complexity of the topic and the need for specific measures of human capital in the academic context led us to design systematic and rigorous empirical work comprising different stages.

The (i) first stage focused on identifying the key attributes that make up academic human capital and designing a research questionnaire. The design of the questionnaire began with an exploratory qualitative phase, building a measurement scale about scientific human capital from an expert's perspective of a panel of leading scholars. The Delphi methodology was developed to obtain expert consensus on the relevant items that needed to be introduced in the scale. During the (ii) second stage, we empirically validated the measurement tool extracted from the Delphi technique. Based on the principles of methodological triangulation, the combination of two or more research methods in the study of a phenomenon contributes to a deeper interpretation and convergence of the results obtained (Jick, 1979). Finally, in the (iii) third stage, we developed a k-means cluster analysis that was conducted to identify and describe the groups of academics in the sample. To identify the relationship between these identified profiles and their IRC levels, ANOVA tests were also conducted.

3.1. Stage 1: survey design and data collection

3.1.1. Delphi panel and the development of the questionnaire

The Delphi technique was used to achieve consensus among specialists on human capital in the academic context (Landeta, 2006; Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004). This technique presents a structured, iterative process in which experts share their anonymous opinions in subsequent phases. Two aspects are especially relevant when proposing this type of analysis. On the one hand, to delimit the topic on which it is intended to find a consensus among the experts. Specifically, our study was developed between 2014 and 2018 to examine relevant aspects of intellectual capital and its management in public universities as part of a broader funded project. Given that the objective of this research project was to identify and categorize the elements that are key in the development of research activity and to inspire debate, eight open questions on intellectual capital, research policies, resources, and incentives were proposed (Appendix A). The second key aspect is the identification and selection of experts who should participate in the panel. Following Okoli and Pawlowski (2004), to avoid response biases and subjectivity problems derived from this method, we established different criteria for the

selection of the panel of experts. In this sense, we selected scientific team leaders who met two conditions: (i) scientific team leaders recognized by the Spanish National Plan for Scientific Research, Development, and Technological Innovation (National R + D + i Plan) and (ii) active research activity, according to their scientific productivity records. Once these selection criteria were established, we contacted the leaders of these scientific teams by telephone to inform them of the purpose of the study and to request their participation. Finally, 62 leading scholars comprised the expert panel that participated in the design of the survey and measures (20 in the arts and humanities, 18 in the sciences, 8 in the health sciences, 6 in the law and social sciences, and 10 in engineering and architecture). In the first step, to initially inspire discussion and debate, the expert panel responded to eight open-ended questions about intellectual capital in universities, from which 40 preliminary factors related to researcher human capital were obtained. In order to reach consensus among the experts regarding the objective of the Delphi technique, we tried to synthesize the opinions after each round (Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004). The experts twice examined this preliminary set of factors to confirm their opinions about the proposed factors. After three rounds of discussion, the experts reached a consensus on the different topics that arose from the open-ended questions.

Through the information obtained in the Delphi analysis, the final set of items was designed as a five-point Likert scale survey (1 = completely disagree, 5 = completely agree). Examples of the items included “I have the necessary theoretical training to conduct research within my scientific field” and “I know the most relevant publications within my scientific field.” To design the research questionnaire, a pre-test was also conducted to guarantee the clarity of the proposed items, reducing the potential misunderstanding of respondents when the data collection was carried out. Specifically, the survey was pretested by sending it to 62 team leaders who actively participated in the study.

In this draft of the questionnaire, all the items were accompanied by an open text box in which the respondent was asked to include as much information as they considered relevant in relation to the item, from the wording to any type of suggestion that seemed relevant. All comments and suggestions received were analyzed by the authors during the design of the final survey.

However, prior to the survey, in addition to this pre-test, we also placed special emphasis on *ex-ante* procedures or procedural remedies to avoid and reduce possible biases (Podsakoff et al., 2012). Following Podsakoff et al.'s (2012) recommendations, (i) the data on the dependent variables were collected using external sources. Specifically, the data referring to scientific productivity were collected from the data provided by Elsevier's Scopus. (ii) Moreover, to decrease the tendency of respondents to provide socially desirable responses, voluntary identification of the interviewees was requested at the end of the questionnaire. However, anonymity was guaranteed to all scientific respondents, endorsing the use of their responses solely for the purpose of the research. (iii) Likewise, we were quite careful in writing the items, reducing ambiguous and unclear items, vague concepts, and complex wording. In addition to considering the proposals of the experts in the previous pre-test process, to confirm the understanding and reduction of any ambiguity, we designed the questions to be simple and concise, defining ambiguous terms, and providing examples. (iv) Finally, the scale items of each variable predictor in the questionnaire were separated and not labeled on the basis of the reported constructs.

3.1.2. Data collection process

The data collection process started after the Delphi panel concluded the survey design. The mailing process began in February 2017, when the vice rectorate for research at the University of Cádiz emailed the vice rectorates for research at other Spanish public universities. The purpose of the email was to request the collaboration of academics in responding to our questionnaire, and it included a clarifying letter about the research and its purposes. A link to the online survey was included in the email to be forwarded to academics. This link was redirected to a virtual

survey through the SurveyMonkey platform. Using the SurveyMonkey platform allowed us to have direct control over submissions and responses from the respondents.

This first mailing process generated 1174 preliminary valid responses. Subsequently, a second mailing process with a reminder note was sent, which prompted valid data for 1722 preliminary responses.

However, to define the final sample, we developed a first filter in which we extracted from the sample those respondents who identified themselves by name or ORCID to collect their publication records and the international collaboration they had developed. After this first filtering, we also selected those academics who held an academic rank with specific research tasks (full professor, professor, associate professor, assistant professor, post-doctoral researchers, and pre-doctoral researchers). Finally, we achieved a final sample of 937 academics. In particular, the composition of the sample was as follows:

- Academic ranks: full professors (24 %), professors (38.5 %), associate professors (15.5 %), assistant professors (6.2 %), post-doctoral researchers (6.6 %), and pre-doctoral researchers (8.3 %).
- Scientific fields: arts and humanities (17.8 %), sciences (33.1 %), health sciences (4.3 %), social and legal sciences (24.1 %), and engineering and architecture (20.8 %).
- Gender: 57.4 % men and 42.6 % women.

3.1.3. Spanish research system

This study is part of a broader research project (ECO2014-56580-R) funded by the Spanish Ministry for Science and Technology (Non-Oriented Fundamental Research Projects Subprogram). This funded project was developed between 2014 and 2018 to examine relevant aspects of intellectual capital and its management in public universities. Therefore, the fundamental objective of this project motivated the use of Spanish academics as the research sample.

The Spanish research system has developed significant modifications over the past few decades. Since the approval of profound reforms in 2001 (LOU, 6/2001), and similar to other European countries, higher education institutions have enjoyed greater autonomy, and research productivity has played a key role in career advancement. In the Spanish research system, as in other European countries with centralized university systems, academics are subject to the same regulations and incentive systems set by the national government. According to the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), Spanish scientific productivity for the period 2006–2019 (COVID-19 pre-pandemic data) and the global scientific impact of Spanish publications are above the world average, since Spanish scientific production is cited 20 % more than the world average. In addition, according to the Elsevier Scopus database, 59.8 % of the Spanish scientific production documents were published in the best journals in each area. Likewise, more than half of Spanish scientific production (56 % in Web of Science and 50.4 % in Scopus) was the result of international collaboration, which continues to grow year after year. Therefore, we found the analysis of the scientific human capital used to achieve these results especially interesting. However, we believe that future studies could compare our results with those obtained in other contexts. In this way, the absolute generalizability of our findings could be tested.

3.2. Stage 2: measures and methods

The next step before conducting the cluster analysis was to examine the sample in regard to the descriptive statistics and normality of the data. In this case, the data followed a non-normal distribution. Subsequently, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to analyze the internal structure of the collected data in the questionnaire (Table 1). The EFA provided five **human capital** dimensions, confirming the KSA framework (Becker, 1962). Hence, items 1–7 were labeled *research abilities* (abilities), 8–11 were labeled *scientific knowledge* (knowledge), 12–14 were labeled *functional skills* (skills), 15–18 were

Table 1
Exploratory factor analysis.

	Factors				
	1	2	3	4	5
	Research abilities	Scientific knowledge	Functional skills	Entrepreneurial skills	Critical thinking
1. I know how to present and communicate my research findings	0.778				
2. I am able to fluently relate to other researchers	0.763				
3. I know how to manage research activities (thesis, research projects)	0.738				
4. I am able to carry out research on my own	0.710				
5. I know how to link observations with test results and come out with conclusions	0.650				
6. I am able to adapt to changes within my research context	0.597				
7. I am able to identify research themes within my research context	0.590				
8. I have the necessary training in research methodologies and techniques		0.810			
9. I have the necessary theoretical training to conduct research within my scientific field		0.787			
10. I know the most relevant publication within my scientific field		0.626			
11. I have the required skill to obtain and manage the necessary information for the research		0.625			
12. Disciplined			0.881		
13. Organized			0.820		
14. Perseverant			0.673		
15. Creative				0.777	
16. Has initiative				0.671	
17. Observation skills				0.566	
18. Inspired				0.549	
19. Able to accept criticism					0.744
20. Self-critical					0.741
21. Altruistic					0.558
Eigenvalue	7.317	2.135	1.283	1.137	1.006
Explained variance	34.843 %	10.168 %	6.109 %	5.416 %	4.791 %
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.908			
Cronbach's alpha		0.894			

labeled *entrepreneurial skills* (skills), and 19–21 were labeled *critical thinking* (skills). The Cronbach's alpha of the scale was 0.894. We also checked for human capital dimensions' significance as Table 2 shows.

To measure IRC, we take a view based on joint scientific results, adopting an approach that understands the concept of IRC as an international co-authorship of scientific publications (Adams, 2013; Kwiek, 2020). In this sense, the concept of international collaboration is defined from a bibliometric perspective since it supports the fact that researchers from two or more nations share their names as authors of a scientific publication (Abramo et al., 2011). In fact, co-authorship publishing has been widely accepted in the literature as one of the most tangible and popular IRC indicators because it is (1) objective and verifiable and (2) a practical and easy way to quantify international collaboration, and (3) there are data available on a large scale in the most relevant databases (Kato and Ando, 2013; Chen et al., 2019).

We actually used the IRC index provided by Scival (Elsevier) included in the snowball metrics. These metrics are defined and endorsed by research-intensive universities (University of College London, University of Oxford, University of Cambridge, and Imperial College London, among others) with the objective to create reliable and objective measures that allow comparisons between different institutions and consider a wide set of research activities.

Finally, we used the **h-index** to measure researcher productivity. Although it presents different limitations, a number of advantages are recognized. Among them, Hirsch (2005) highlights that the h-index

Table 2
ANOVA (human capital dimensions).

	F	Sig.
Research abilities	649.291	0.000
Scientific knowledge	519.881	0.000
Functional skills	12.292	0.000
Entrepreneurial skills	14.711	0.000
Critical thinking	21.010	0.000

considers the quantity and impact of publications, and it is quite simple to interpret (Alonso et al., 2009). In addition, the h-index has a very practical access through Thomson ISI Web of Science or Elsevier's SCOPUS (Hirsch, 2005). It is particularly useful because of its objectivity (Costas and Bordons, 2007) in regard to comparative descriptions of scientific topics (Banks, 2006), journal assessment (Braun et al., 2006), and avoiding the effect of rarely cited papers (Vanclay, 2007). However, in order to check the robustness and validity of our results when using this index, the relationship between the identified clusters and their level of scientific productivity was also analyzed using other academic performance variables. For example, the FWCI (*Field Weight Citation Impact*), the number of publications, the M-Index, the H5-Index or the number of publications in Top 25 % percentile journals within each scientific field. Replication of these analyzes showed similar results.

3.3. Stage 3: cluster analysis

As previously indicated, despite the fact that IRC has been widely studied, the description of the human capital of researchers who collaborate internationally has not been studied in depth.

In this sense, as this study proposes an alternative view of the extant studies in order to examine academic human capital using a profile approach, an exploratory analysis of the data was conducted (Hsu and Sandford, 2007), providing empirical evidence for different academic profiles by applying a cluster analysis of the IRC context (Alverson and Skolberg, 2000).

Therefore, a k-means cluster analysis was conducted to identify the different groups in the sample. This technique allows for finding internally consistent and conceptually interpretable profiles that present clear external differences (Schmitt et al., 2007). The groups should be large enough to represent a relevant cluster, showing the external differences in a number of cases in the sample. To make the selection of groups easier, a hierarchical cluster analysis was applied, as recommended by Ketchen and Shook (1996), to examine the dendrogram and

the number of cases per cluster.

3.4. Cluster analysis

3.4.1. Results

As previously explained, cluster analysis is a technique inherently linked to the concept of similarity, since its objective is to identify homogeneous subgroups of cases in a given sample (Ketchen and Shook, 1996). Once we verified that the five factors of scientific human capital were significant based on the ANOVA tests (Table 2), a k-means cluster analysis was developed.

The conceptual meaning of the subgroups and the evaluation of the results concluded that the optimal number of subgroups were three different profiles of academics that we interpreted and described in the following section (Fig. 1): Cluster 1 (Consolidated international research collaborators), Cluster 2 (Effective international research collaborators) and Cluster 3 (Skilled international research collaborators).

In order to identify the relationship between these three identified profiles and their IRC levels, ANOVA tests were conducted. Similarly, to increase our knowledge of these profiles, ANOVA tests were also developed to analyze, from an exploratory view, the relationships between these clusters and their level of scientific productivity (*h-index*). The information provided by these ANOVA tests allowed us to be more precise in the description of these profiles, identifying the groups of scientists who collaborated the most internationally and who were the most productive in relation to the description of their scientific human capital. This valuable information to describe the academic profiles was also complemented with information on the composition of these clusters based on descriptive data, such as the gender of the members, the area of knowledge, or the academic rank (Table 3).

Cluster 1 (*Consolidated international research collaborators*) is the most abundant profile among the scientists in the sample. Specifically, it comprised 476 scientists. This cluster is mainly composed of academics who have tenured positions or full professor rank, as 86.4 % of the academics held this academic rank. Moreover, in this group, most academics belonged to the “science” scientific field (35.2 %), 61.3 % of the group were men, and 59 % had more than 20 years of experience. Regarding the description of the human capital profile of the researchers in this cluster, most academics had relatively high and positive scores in *scientific knowledge* and *research skills* (*hard skills*) (Table 4). As for the

Table 3
Cluster description.

Clusters		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Scientific field	Art and humanities	21.1 %	16.7 %	12.1 %
	Sciences	35.2 %	35.1 %	26.8 %
	Social and legal sciences	19.0 %	21.2 %	35.6 %
	Health sciences	4.9 %	4.5 %	3.3 %
	Engineering & Architecture	19.8 %	22.5 %	22.2 %
Experience	Less than 5 years	3.6 %	18.6 %	9.7 %
	From 5 to 10 years	9.7 %	21.3 %	12.2 %
	From 11 to 15 years	12.2 %	16.7 %	15.1 %
	From 16 to 20 years	15.5 %	11.3 %	14.7 %
	More than 20 years	59.0 %	32.1 %	48.3 %
Academic Rank	Full professor	33.4 %	11.3 %	16.7 %
	Tenure positions	53.0 %	47.3 %	61.5 %
	Early career academics	11.8 %	21.2 %	11.7 %
	Pre-doctoral researchers	1.9 %	20.3 %	10.0 %
Gender	Men	61.3 %	53.2 %	55.3 %
	Woman	38.7 %	46.8 %	44.7 %

Table 4
Comparison of academic profiles (*cluster analysis*).

	Cluster		
	1 (N = 476)	2 (N = 222)	3 (N = 239)
Research abilities	0.40771	-1.36746	0.45819
Scientific knowledge	0.60112	-0.04182	-1.15836
Functional skills	0.12132	0.02573	-0.26553
Entrepreneurial skills	0.16693	-0.23394	-0.11517
Critical thinking	0.07770	-0.36389	0.18327

rest of the scientific skills (*soft skills*), this group of academics is also characterized by the highest and most positive scores in *entrepreneurial skills*. The ANOVA tests performed to analyze the relationship between this cluster and the *h-index* and IRC show that this profile has the highest level of scientific productivity and scientific collaboration (Tables 5 and 6).

Cluster 2 (*Effective international research collaborators*) comprised 222 scientists, of whom 46.8 % were women. The human capital profile of this group of academics presents low scores in most human capital dimensions. The lack of scores for *research competences* (*hard skills*) was

Fig. 1. Comparison between clusters.

Table 5
ANOVA (h-index-clusters).

H-Index					F	Sig.			
					17.100	0.000			
					95 % confidence interval		Min.	Max.	
					Lower bound	Upper bound			
H-Index	1	457	12.35	11.504	0.538	11.29	13.41	0	74
	2	208	7.98	7.623	0.529	6.94	9.02	0	37
	3	219	8.79	9.195	0.621	7.57	10.01	0	49
	Total	884	10.44	10.336	0.348	9.76	11.12	0	74

Table 6
ANOVA (IRC-clusters).

International Collaboration					F	Sig.			
					8.294	0.000			
					95 % confidence interval		Min.	Max.	
					Lower bound	Upper bound			
International Collaboration	1	457	16.09	29.705	1.390	13.36	18.82	0	305
	2	208	8.94	17.433	1.209	6.55	11.32	0	138
	3	219	9.44	20.794	1.405	6.67	12.21	0	181
	Total	884	12.76	25.409	0.855	11.08	14.44	0	305

especially evident in this cluster, showing the lowest level of the three clusters (Table 4). In the same vein, this cluster obtained the worst scores in other *research skills (soft skills)*, such as *entrepreneurial skills* and *critical thinking* skills. Although science academics stood out (35.1 %), the cluster was relatively balanced in terms of other scientific fields, such as engineering and architecture (22.5 %) and the social and legal sciences (21.2 %). Regarding the professional category of this group of researchers, we found two different sets of academics: those who held tenure positions (47.3 %) and those who were pre-doctoral researchers (20.3 %). The results of the ANOVA test suggest that, in terms of productivity, this cluster is the least productive of the three clusters identified. Likewise, according to the findings of the ANOVA test, this group of academics is the least interested in IRC (Tables 5 and 6).

Cluster 3 (*Skilled international research collaborators*) included 239 academics, of whom 44.7 % were women. Within this cluster, the academics showed the highest level of *research competencies (hard skills)*, although they scored very low in terms of *scientific knowledge* and relatively low in terms of *functional skills* and *entrepreneurial skills* (Table 4). In this group, most academics belonged to the social and legal sciences (35.6 %) and sciences (26.8 %). Regarding the academic rank of this group of researchers, this cluster is mainly composed of academics who have tenured positions or full professor ranks, as 78.2 % of the academics held these academic positions. The ANOVA tests performed to analyze the relationship between this cluster and the h-index and IRC levels show that this profile has low levels of scientific productivity and scientific collaboration with respect to the other clusters (Tables 5 and 6).

4. Discussion and conclusions

This study presents an exploratory analysis and preliminary conclusions on academic profiles of human capital and IRC intensity. As pointed out in the literature review, multiple studies have analyzed the cause-and-effect relationships from different IRC antecedents that define a researcher with “internationalist” conditions compared to a more “localist” view (Kwiek, 2018). The literature substantially supports the argument that a researcher’s tendency to collaborate internationally ultimately depends on individual factors (Kato and Ando, 2017; Wagner et al., 2018). That is, IRC depends to a greater extent on individual values and attributes more than on institutions, governments, or

academic disciplines (Wagner et al., 2018; Finkelstein et al., 2013).

However, the literature has focused on more specific characteristics and attributes that condition the development of international collaboration without finding a clear consensus regarding the attributes that define the construct of scientific human capital (Abramo et al., 2017). We believe that this study contributes to the IRC literature by providing an alternative point of view to complete the understanding of the determinants of IRC.

Drawing on the results, we found three groups that responded to the different realities of researchers in IRC through the k-means cluster analysis (Fig. 1). Specifically, we extracted the three following different academic profiles: *consolidated international research collaborators (cluster 1)*, *effective international research collaborators (cluster 2)*, and *(3) skilled international research collaborators (cluster 3)*.

4.1. CLUSTER 1: consolidated international research collaborators

This group of scholars is mainly defined by a balanced high profile of scientific human capital. As shown, the scores are higher in those dimensions of human capital that can be considered most essential for research (Fig. 1). These attributes are related to what the literature defines as “hard skills” (De Frutos-Belizón et al., 2020). Hence, the researchers in this group have a relatively high and positive score in scientific knowledge and research skills.

According to the measures used, cluster 1’s scores may indicate that the academics in this group might have key competencies, such as identifying research topics, discussing and interpreting results, and being very active in most research tasks (Ulrich and Dash, 2013; Thunnissen and Van Arensbergen, 2015). The findings also indicate that they may possess extensive theoretical and methodological knowledge and can identify relevant journals and publications in their field. It is likely that these researchers publish and review the literature periodically. Regarding the rest of the scientific skills (soft skills), it is also observed that this group of academics can develop research from a proactive perspective and accept criticism from others.

In addition, the preliminary results obtained in terms of productivity suggest that this group is particularly productive since they have the highest h-index (Table 5). As we have indicated previously, the ANOVA tests also confirmed that this cluster obtained the best IRC scores, making it the group that most collaborates internationally, with a

relevant difference with respect to the other two clusters (Table 6).

These findings are coherent with the previous literature in the field. As Kwiek (2016) points out, international collaboration emerges as one of the most relevant predictors of research productivity. Although this relationship could not necessarily be understood as strictly causal, the literature shows that the most productive scientists are more visible in an international context (Kwiek, 2020).

This human capital profile leads us to consider that the researchers are particularly focused on and involved in research. They assume their responsibility as scientists to contribute to science, and they are highly recognized (prestige) among peers and colleagues—all this in addition to performing other academic tasks.

It can be said that, during their academic careers, these researchers have developed skills to make them “attractive” to other researchers or teams at the international level. As explained, IRC demands having sufficient levels of “hard skills” to be considered as a potential international collaborator. In this vein, Wagner et al. (2018) argues that IRC is a self-organized network system that allows collaborators to select their research partners. The dynamics of IRC are based on the phenomenon of preferential attachment; that is, international collaboration networks are formed around key academics who are attractive for their knowledge, research skills, and/or resources (Wagner, 2018). Therefore, it is the system itself that does not allow opportunism among peers and, at the same time, increases the visibility and collaborative success of researchers who have greater research competencies. Obviously, this greater visibility and prestige also help them to have reached more advanced stages in their academic career.

As the results also show, having an important stock of knowledge (methodological or not) places academics in a good position to complement other researchers. Moreover, these researchers have the ability to interact fluently with other researchers, something that allows them to establish relationships at international conferences and get involved in international research networks (Melin, 2000). Similarly, they have the necessary skills to lead research projects, which may make it easier for them to get involved in international research projects.

Definitively, as the literature shows, these attributes are related to individual competencies necessary to carry out research in a social context (Seibert et al., 2017), promoting IRC. Therefore, it is possible to posit that this group understands research as a social phenomenon that is executed through collaborative research in scientific teams and international research networks (Brew et al., 2016).

Furthermore, we understand that this configuration, characterized by a balanced structure of the different dimensions of scientific human capital, can benefit from a feedback effect on the researcher’s own knowledge and skills. As the researcher develops his/her research career supported by these collaborations, their stock of knowledge and skills increases, which increases his/her prestige and international visibility.

In essence, this cluster presents traditional attributes, not only demographic but also intrinsic ones, that define a clear international collaborator profile, as Kwiek (2020) noted. In this group (476 academics), most academics present more than 20 years of experience (59 %), since the majority of researchers are university professors or university holders (72.3 %). As the literature shows, academics who tend to collaborate internationally have more experience and better networks (Jung et al., 2014; Kwiek, 2020). In addition, researchers who hold higher professional positions also have more resources in terms of “power, prestige, visibility and scientific position” in their field of knowledge (Rostan and Ceravolo, 2015: 257), making them more attractive profiles from which to develop IRC.

The results are also consistent with previous findings in the literature regarding the scientific field of researchers—35.1 % of researchers in the sciences—that those belonging to the “hard-sciences” are 2.3 times more likely to be highly internationalized than those belonging to the “soft” fields of knowledge (Finkelstein and Sethi, 2014).

Therefore, as can be seen in Fig. 1, our preliminary results lead us to consider this combination of attributes of scientific human capital as the

most appropriate profile for the development of IRC and obtaining better research results, reinforcing the proposed “human capital profile” approach. Although the cluster shows positive scores on human capital attributes, not all of them are particularly high. That is, the profile presents a balanced combination of human capital attributes. This reinforces the notion that more human capital is not always better but rather a mix and levels of certain core attributes that ensure the underpinnings of IRC.

4.2. CLUSTER 2: effective international research collaborators

This cluster presents low scores in most of the human capital dimensions. In particular, compared to the rest of the clusters, the lack of research competencies is especially relevant, showing the lowest level of the three clusters (Fig. 1). These preliminary findings and the composition of the academics allow us to reach the following twofold conclusion:

- (1) It is possible that *researchers in tenure positions* no longer have an active attitude toward research after having reached permanent job positions. This may indicate that they are not updated in terms of the scientific knowledge in the field, methodologies, new theoretical approaches, top and relevant journals, etc. This situation may also explain their low scores in regard to functional skills related to how they develop research activities. That is, they seem to lack work routines and organized procedures for conducting research because they are no longer researching, such as being “stuck” in their academic career by having reached a tenure position or being researchers who have adopted a passive attitude toward research. In the same vein, this cluster obtained the worst scores in terms of entrepreneurial skills, which includes items related to motivation for research, creative capacities, and initiative in research. These arguments find support when analyzing the professional categories of the academics that make up this group. A high number of researchers in this group were associate professors (29.3 %) and assistant professors (18 %), both tenure positions. Although it is true that the knowledge scores of this group are close to the average, it is probably because these researchers have accumulated this scientific knowledge over the course of their academic career.

Examining the number of six-year terms (“*ssexenios*” in the Spanish context), the data show that 47.8 % of the researchers have no six-year terms. Based on the fact that six-year terms are a useful tool in the Spanish research context to analyze the continuity in the development of research, it can be seen that a part of this group of academics stopped actively developing research. In a way, this lack of motivation is also reflected in the lack of research competencies since this is the group of researchers that obtained the worst score in our analyses. These competencies can be considered basic for the development of any international collaboration. The findings for this group of academics also reflect that this cluster has the least interest in IRC. Probably, this lack of interest in research translates into more occasional international collaborations, all of them originating in earlier, more productive stages in the academic career. In addition, the preliminary results obtained in terms of productivity suggest that this group is the least productive of the three clusters identified, something that is supported by the results of the ANOVA test (Tables 5 and 6).

The literature establishes that IRC has two fundamental prerequisites, individual motivation and the “attractiveness” (referring to research competencies) of researchers to their international colleagues (Kyvik and Larsen, 1994; Kato and Ando, 2017; Kwiek, 2020).

It is likely that this lack of motivation or interest toward research causes the researcher to lose a large part of those

research competences to develop IRC. For instance, if a researcher is not regularly updated in terms of the literature published in their field of knowledge, they will hardly be able to demonstrate skills related to the identification of research topics in their discipline.

Likewise, it will be difficult for them to demonstrate skills to lead competitive research projects. This implies that researchers may lose visibility and attractiveness in terms of their international colleagues. Hence, apart from losing “attractive” research competences, researchers may stop attending international workshops and conferences or leading international research projects. In other words, these researchers are prone to lose the basic and necessary potential to join international research networks (Wagner and Leydesdorff, 2005).

- (2) *Pre-doctoral researchers* who are at the beginning of their academic careers are still acquiring and developing research skills, knowledge, and competences. In this case, the lack of human capital actually exists, but the reasons and the implications behind that fact are quite different from tenured academics. Training and funds oriented to foster mobility and network generation are crucial in this stage of one’s academic career (Horta and Santos, 2016; Horta et al., 2018).

In essence, the fact that they are in the process of training does not allow them to be visible internationally. This is a group of researchers who should complement their human capital through international collaborations. However, to ensure their “attractiveness” to other international colleagues for collaboration, a minimum level of research competences should be present. Otherwise, an imbalanced situation in terms of the contribution to the collaboration between both parts may appear, leading to inefficiencies or even conflicts (Cummings and Kiesler, 2007).

Although mobility between junior and pre-doctoral researchers has increased in recent years (Laudel and Bielick, 2019), these first contacts do not usually generate collaborative publications. Rather, the orientation of mobility in these early stages of the academic career has a formative purpose. Therefore, it is possible that these initial contacts will be strengthened over time to generate future collaborations.

Furthermore, international collaborations for early-stage researchers are usually less successful compared to other “local” and even “institutional” collaborations. These arguments find support in the literature since normally older academic generations group the largest proportion of scientists who collaborate internationally (Jeong et al., 2014). This should not be surprising since it is evident that IRC requires time to develop and strengthen the social ties that sustain it.

All the presented arguments are also reinforced when paying attention to the seniority of academics in the cluster. In particular, 39.9 % were researchers with less than 10 years of experience—understood as those years from the beginning of the doctorate—while 32.1 % had more than 20 years of experience. In the same way, regarding the professional category of this group of researchers, we find two different sets of academics: those who held tenure positions (47.3 %) and those who were pre-doctoral researchers (20.3 %). As observed, the confluence of both types of researchers in the same cluster, being in the opposite stages of their career, leads to a particularly unskilled group to carry out IRC at that point in time. In fact, the scores obtained on IRC may relate to previous stages of tenured researchers’ careers, in which they collaborated internationally with the single aim to reach permanent positions.

4.3. CLUSTER 3: skilled international research collaborators

As we have previously indicated, this group of researchers showed the highest level of research competencies although they scored very

low in terms of scientific knowledge and relatively low in terms of functional skills and entrepreneurial skills (Fig. 1). The researchers of this cluster seem to have the core attributes on which IRC is built (research competences), but it may be possible that they do not have enough time to do research, leading them to be notably out-of-date in regard to different dimensions of research knowledge; they do not have precise and organized work routines; and/or even that they are not interested in finding new research topics or proposing new lines of research.

This combination of attributes, a priori, may indicate that they are researchers who should compensate for their significant lack of scientific knowledge by establishing collaborations with other colleagues (Seibert et al., 2017). In fact, the low level of knowledge—theoretical and methodological knowledge, knowledge of top journals, and data collection and management information—is particularly noteworthy compared to the other two clusters.

For example, it can be the case of researchers who develop other academic functions such as management tasks or contracts with firms. They could have the research skills necessary to carry out research and to be “attractive” to potential collaborators but not the necessary knowledge or dynamics to do the work. An academic can focus on any of the other university missions throughout their academic career, affecting the degree to which they collaborate nationally and internationally. Academic reward systems do not always “reward” the development of these other missions (Fochler et al., 2016), hindering performance indicators.

For instance, a researcher who spends most of their time on signing transfer contracts with companies or on writing books or reports for practitioners will not be valued in the same way as those who invest all their time conducting research.

All this means that the researcher does not have the necessary skills or the time to gain visibility and be “attractive” to their international colleagues. As Katz and Martin (1997) argue, the more researchers and institutions that are involved in scientific collaboration, the greater are the efforts required to manage the research. In the case of IRC, the necessary efforts and resources would increase (Cummings and Kiesler, 2007).

According to the theory of resource allocation, the resources that a researcher in terms of commitment and time can dedicate to research will have limitations. As stated by Jeong et al. (2014: 522), “the resources allocated to a function will decrease as resources allocated to other functions increase.” For example, Finkelstein and Sethi (2014) showed that academics who were primarily focused on university teaching tasks were half as likely to collaborate internationally. This lack of commitment and time to fully dedicate to research tasks has a double negative effect on IRC. On one hand, researchers do not have the resources or the time to attend international research conferences or carry out research stays, for example. On the other hand, researchers are not actively engaged in research, and this reduces their own stock of knowledge and other attributes of academic human capital, which makes them less visible internationally.

In a way, this lack of continuity in doing research is also supported by the results of the ANOVA test, where up to 47.9 % of the researchers who make up this cluster have only one six-year term (*sexenio*) or none at all.

Therefore, we could think that this group of researchers should have a greater propensity to collaborate internationally for the following two main reasons: 1) they show important levels of research competences, which makes them capable of doing research and also of being “attractive” to other potential collaborators, and 2) they lack, overall, relevant knowledge—theoretical and methodological knowledge, knowledge of top journals, and knowledge of data collection and management information—on the field, limiting them from developing any line of work. As mentioned, they have limited time to focus on these tasks. This would explain why the cluster presents the lowest functional skills, referring to having work routines and discipline and being organized at doing research.

From the discussion of the obtained clusters, we noted that main differences appear between clusters 1 and 2. In fact, they both show almost opposite profiles of human capital. The first cluster presents experienced, research-active, and highly skilled researchers. By contrast, cluster 2 includes researchers who are in the early stages of their careers, receiving training and acquiring competencies and researchers who seem to be disconnected from research and showing a passive attitude toward doing research.

Relevant similarities among the groups are also observed and, from our view, could be common issues in any field of research. For example, and aligned with what human capital theory posits, the clusters in which research competences have higher scores (clusters 1 and 3), there are also more relevant IRC indexes (Kwiek, 2018). It can be understood that those specific skills configure as the basis on which IRC is built. Without a minimum level of such competences, a researcher cannot be “attractive” enough to other potential collaborators. In fact, both clusters showed higher levels of IRC and h-index.

We also find that clusters 1 and 2 present certain levels of functional skills, which is supported by the fact that a number of researchers in both clusters and in a way, conduct research as a central part of their daily routines—tenured researchers because they show an active behavior toward research and pre-doctoral researchers because, although they are in a learning stage, they also do research. This would also reflect the importance that conducting research every day leads academics to create and establish routines and organized procedures for doing research as a result of their daily routine.

Finally, the last strong similarity derived from the cluster analysis is related to the general relatively low scores on entrepreneurial skills in all groups. This is important to note because it could suggest that the researchers in the sample would tend to not have a proactive attitude toward searching for collaborations, such as having initiative, being creative in proposing relevant research topics, or even being inspired to conduct research with others.

5. Practical implications, limitations, and future research lines

This paper develops an exploratory study with preliminary findings on different academic human capital profiles and the development of IRC. In particular, we identify several sets of academic traits based on complementary competences that define new typologies of researchers. Our findings reveal that some groups of scientists with a specific set of competences are clearly more internationalized than others. This has allowed us to interpret the characteristics of each cluster that characterize the academic scientific community.

The literature has confirmed that IRC defines the scientific community in terms of academic prestige or access to funding in competitive calls (Kwiek, 2020). Thus, IRC has a stratifying character among scientists that may determine academic career development. In this regard, although several studies have focused on the antecedents of the development of IRC to a greater or lesser extent, there is a clear dispersion on the human capital attributes that determine whether a scientist collaborates internationally. Therefore, in this paper, we have adopted a perspective that examines scientific attributes rather than looking more broadly at the determinants that define IRC. Moreover, this view also challenges the traditional perspective based on the assumption that “more competences or attributes is always better.” From our perspective, we believe that academics should rather have the right combination of scientific skills needed to develop IRC rather than a specific higher number of them. In this context, we propose a typology of academic profiles to examine human capital attributes and the preliminary associated levels of international collaboration.

In the first instance, analyzing the clusters identified in our results confirmed a number of findings consistent with the previous literature. Our results confirmed that the cluster formed by the most international researchers was also the cluster formed by researchers with the most experience and academic status (Kwiek, 2018, 2020). Similarly, our

findings also align with the previous literature on the sensitivity of IRC to the scientific field (Piro et al., 2013; Kwiek, 2020). The cluster of scientists with the most international collaborations (cluster 1) consisted mostly of researchers belonging to the “hard sciences.” Finally, in terms of scientific productivity, we also confirm the findings of previous studies showing that the researchers who collaborated internationally the most were also those with the highest scientific productivity (Abramo et al., 2011; Kwiek, 2020).

Similarly, the identification of a group of academics who possess a variety of potential complementary capacities for IRC development has important practical implications. Over recent decades, science policy makers have tended to favor IRC development in terms of research funding decisions (He, 2009). Thus, the identification of different profiles of human capital attributes that are associated with an increased development of international collaboration can be seen as a valuable contribution. In this sense, we consider that the practical implications of our findings need to be addressed at different levels and by different actors. From one first perspective, the typology of human capital profiles may be of some use to early-career researchers as it can guide them in terms of the research competences needed for the development of international collaboration. Likewise, the proposed typology of profiles can be useful in terms of possible training needs at the beginning of an academic career.

However, the proposed typology of researchers has even more relevant practical implications for the design and implementation of academic staff management policies. For leaders of scientific teams, for example, it is important to know the set of competences that could be complementary among team members in order to encourage international collaboration. In this sense, it also facilitates the identification of synergies between team members, which allows connecting the complementary skills present in different researchers.

Similarly, from the point of view of science policy makers, the profiles identified in this study facilitate the development of science policies that promote IRC in a way that is more specific to the needs of researchers and the scientific fields to which they belong. This perspective is much more useful for the management of scientific human capital than proposing a more homogeneous set of policies without considering the particularities of each researcher profile. For example, management practices in relation to training, research incentives, or scientific mobility could be oriented to more specific needs.

In this sense, based on the cluster identification obtained, we consider that public policies should have a clear orientation toward the development of the potential of cluster 1 (*Consolidated international research collaborators*). As we have seen, this cluster presents experienced, research-active, and highly skilled researchers. Therefore, practices could be implemented to help promote research networks, the development of English language skills, and/or communication skills. While cluster 1 includes highly vocational academics with high levels of human capital, it would be equally interesting to incentivize and motivate international collaboration with the aim of creating stronger and more established research networks (Kyvik and Reymert, 2017). Thus, even if these researchers collaborate internationally on a regular basis, it is important that they do so with the support of a solid network of researchers. To this end, it would also be interesting to encourage scientific mobility through teaching reductions or the possibility of longer sabbatical periods. The promotion of scientific mobility has emerged in recent years as one of the basic pillars on which to sustain levels of scientific performance (Horta et al., 2020). In this sense, it is also relevant to foster communication, ensuring that projects have sufficient funds to guarantee frequent face-to-face meetings as there are stages of more exploratory research that require numerous interdisciplinary discussions. In addition, this allows a broader research vision to be generated among these researchers, generating synergies and complementarities between researchers.

Indeed, given that not all stages of research require the same scientific competences, there is a need to develop efficient tools to manage

the complementarity of skills among researchers. In this sense, as we saw above, also researchers belonging to cluster 3 (Skilled international research collaborators) could compensate for their important lack of scientific knowledge by establishing collaborations with other colleagues. Academics in this cluster could see international collaboration as a relevant tool to complement their more limited human capital profile. In this sense, given that they possess the basic competences to identify and interpret research results, their profile could be complemented by the up-to-date scientific knowledge of the literature possessed by other more proactive researchers with more time available. In addition, the search for this complementarity of competences also makes it possible to address multidisciplinary and its positive effects on research performance (Olmos-Peñuela et al., 2014). Therefore, for both cluster 1 and cluster 3, it would be interesting to develop policies aimed at generating external social capital (Youndt and Snell, 2004).

Finally, with respect to cluster 2 (*Effective international research collaborators*), it would be necessary to implement development policies and practices, mainly those related to motivation and training practices (Youndt and Snell, 2004). For early-career and pre-doctoral researchers, more specific training policies could be applied, such as the application of methodologies or the management of relevant information sources. In this way, their levels of scientific knowledge in their scientific discipline could be raised. For example, seminars on research practices could be offered in order to develop specific scientific knowledge to carry out research in their scientific field. Similarly, it is also necessary to implement policies to “rescue” disassociate researchers. The identification of this group of academics within this cluster shows us that there are human capital profiles that do not favor the development of IRC. These researchers, probably, after reaching permanent positions, have chosen to stop actively conducting research. Therefore, the intrinsic motivation of these academics could be fostered by increasing their understanding of their involvement in research careers and their participation in university missions. Similarly, in these cases, it may also be necessary to facilitate richer communications to socialize this group of researchers.

Alternatively, we also see a need for further research in this field. More research is needed to better understand how researchers’ human capital may condition IRC. In particular, it could be interesting to find out more about how a certain combination of human capital may determine the type of collaboration that is carried out (long-term or short-term collaborations, project collaborations, isolated paper collaborations, etc.).

Another line of research could be related to the way in which human capital affects and is affected by IRC, for example: 1) deepening how human capital accumulates in teams involved in IRC, and 2) examining the synergistic effects of human capital in international teams.

Additionally, we see a need for more research that focuses on analyzing research competences and scientific human capital. One the one hand, different stages that characterize the academic life cycle should be have in mind. In this way, policy packages associated with each stage of the academic career could be designed. Moreover, synergistic effects between human capital dimensions should be also taken into account, trying examine how different human capital attributes interact and affect IRC.

In addition, we believe that more work needs to be done to analyze the relationship between international collaboration and national collaboration. Although some research argues that international collaboration need not come at the expense of domestic collaboration, this dimension has not received the necessary attention in the literature (Jeong et al., 2011). Irrespective of the clusters and the human capital composition that defines each cluster, we also identify that all clusters

have some rate of international collaboration. Therefore, it is also necessary to consider that human capital should not always be identified as a single construct determining the level of IRC. In this sense, it is necessary to develop more studies that analyze the existence of other conditioning factors such as the institutional support provided by the university institution itself and the management policies of its scientific staff. Finally, in this paper we use a sample of Spanish academics. This can be considered as a possible limitation in terms of the generalizability of the findings. Future studies could replicate this work in different national context, with larger datasets. Comparative analyzes would be particularly interesting in this sense, focus on exploring the differences between countries or academic systems, and considering this work a pilot study for the development of future research.

Notes

In Spain, university professors are subject to the same policies and incentive systems established by the national government. For Spanish academics, the most relevant research salary incentive is the six-year period (*sexenios*). To evaluate research performance, an external national committee evaluates the five most relevant high-impact contributions during that six-year period and awards (or not) an official recognition of research performance during that time period. The *sexenios*, in addition to being the main tool by which the Spanish Government evaluates research activity, also represents a monetary bonus for the researcher and added prestige to his/her academic career.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jesús de Frutos-Belizón: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Natalia García Carbonell:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Marta Ruíz-Martínez:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Gonzalo Sánchez-Gardey:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

Sanchez Gardey, Gonzalo reports financial support was provided by University of Cádiz. Sanchez Gardey, Gonzalo reports a relationship with University of Cádiz that includes: employment.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Appendix A. Delphi Questionnaire

To identify those aspects that favor or restrict research activity, we present eight open questions below to obtain your opinion as an expert in your

field of research. Please respond in the spaces below to each question, keeping your area of knowledge in mind:

1. In your opinion, what knowledge, skills, or experiences should a researcher have to carry out their research activities?
2. In research, what role, if any, do the relationships play that the researcher establishes with other researchers both within his or her own university and outside it (research networks, personal relationships with researchers from other universities, scientific meetings, etc.)? How important are these relationships? Do they include researchers from other areas of knowledge?
3. Does your research group have any formalized procedures for the development of the research activity, such as regular meetings, formalized processes, manuals, etc.?
4. Could you indicate what resources are, in your opinion, necessary to carry out the research activity adequately?
5. Can you tell us the main results obtained in your field of research?
6. University activity is defined by three types of tasks: research, teaching, and management. The latter is considered from a broad point of view and is not exclusively circumscribed to the performance of academic positions (e.g., coordination of subjects, management of records, etc.). Please describe how these three types of tasks influence each other. Feel free to use examples to explain your answer
7. If it were up to you, what policies and actions should universities take to improve research results in their scientific fields?
8. And in the field of regional and national policies?

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix B. Human capital literature review

KSA framework	Concepts	Literature
<i>Knowledge</i>	Attributes related to researchers' theoretical and methodological understanding, researchers' comprehension to find, researchers' English (or other predominant languages in the field of research) language domain, manage information from relevant publications in their field of research and know relevant publications in the scientific field, etc.	Bozeman et al. (2001) Hautala (2011) Horta and Santos (2016) Jacob and Lefgren (2011) Lee et al. (2010) Lovitts (2005) Mooken and Sugden (2014) Prpić (1996) Su (2011) Tiam et al. (2009)
<i>Skills</i>	Attributes referred to the researcher's creativity, initiative and motivation to carry out the research activity, constancy, discipline and organization at the research workplace, self-criticism, etc.	Barnacle and Dall'Alba (2014) Bazeley (2010) Bentley and Kyvik (2013) Marie (2008) McNie et al. (2016) Neumann (2006) Timmerman et al. (2011) Thunnissen and Van Arensbergen (2015) Ulrich and Dash (2013a) Wang et al. (2006) White et al. (2012) Whitelock et al. (2008)
<i>Abilities</i>	Research-specific context attributes of individuals to observe facts and identify research topics, discuss research results, interact with other researchers, know how conduct and autonomously develop research and adapt to changes in the research context, etc.	Bozeman et al. (2013) Drummond and Fischhoff (2017) Durette et al. (2016) Kyvik (2013) Marie (2008) Timmerman et al. (2011)

Source: Own elaboration adapted from García-Carbonell et al. (2021).

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